

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYMER LIQUID CRYSTAL (PLC) REINFORCED BY BIOGLASS FIBERS OR POWDER IN APPLICATION ON ORTHOPEDIC SCREWS

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SUMMARY: Polymer liquid crystals (PLCs) constitute an important class of polymeric materials with advantageous properties. They are particularly useful in applications in which high service temperatures, high resistance to deformation and low thermal conductivity are required. As compared to engineering plastics, PLCs show clearly superiority with regard to chemical resistance, low flammability, high modulus and often unusual ease of processing. PLCs include a rigid reinforcement connected with a flexible matrix by primary chemical bonds; thus both kinds of sequences appear inside the same PLC copolymer chains. Since PET has been used as a biomaterial and PHB is an inert material, PLC here is tested as promising biomaterial. The experimental material - copolymer of poly(ethylene) terephthalate PET + 0.6 mole fraction of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid PHB further in the text denoted as PET/0.6 PHB belongs to longitudinal thermotropic PLCs, the simplest type, with rodlike mesogens in the backbone and oriented along the backbone. The PLC pellets were put through a high-speed thrashing machine and turned into a fibrous mass to avoid pre-aligning. This fibrous form of the PLC was kept in the temperature of 100⁰C for five hours to remove any excess water in a desiccator, before shaping. Glass fibres was provided by Cracow Academy of Mining with fibre diameter range 7 - 9 μm, average 8 μm, fibre length - 3 mm; data obtained with optical microscope Lanometr. It was tested four kinds of composite materials with 10, 15 and 25% of glass fibres and 10% of glass powder + PET/0.6 PHB. Besides was tested another type of PLC – PLA: poly(L-lactic acid) produced by DOW-Cargill (USA) and reinforced by 15% of glass fibre. Using in tests dumbbell samples were injected at temperature 180⁰–200⁰C. Mechanical properties like tensile strength, stress e-modulus and stress relaxation were tested using Instron universal machine. Conductivity test was carried out in distil water. The orthopedic screws (thread MW II-geometric was modelling using FEM) were injected from experimental material at the temperature of 185 °C. Screws were planted into the bone, test was repeated with human bone as a counter-sample what simulated implantation case. Moment of torsion was obtained as a moment when the screw was destroyed. This test was done with using a special stand constructed on Technical University of Cracow. Results obtained during the tests point at necessary reinforce matrix LPC polymers (PLA and PET/0,6PHB) by bioglass fibres that to get a better straight and modulus. Tests of the ultimate torment momentum for bone - screw junction and shear with the direction along thread show that PLA is material which can be more using in application on orthopedic screws. It tries to make a material for orthopedic screws, which will have proprieties much similar to the bone.

KEYWORDS: Biomedical applications, Ceramic matrix composites, Mechanical & physical properties, Reinforcements

INTRODUCTION

Polymer liquid crystals (PLCs) constitute an important class of polymeric materials with advantageous properties stated for instance by de Gennes e.a. in [1], one of us in [2] or Hess e.a. in [3]. They are particularly useful in applications in which high service temperatures, high resistance to deformation and low thermal expansivity are required. As compared to engineering plastics, PLCs show clearly superiority with regard to chemical resistance, low flammability, high modulus and often unusual ease of processing, investigated for in by Hwang in [4]. PLCs include a rigid reinforcement (LC sequences) connected with a flexible matrix (flexible sequences) by primary chemical bonds; thus both kinds of

sequences appear inside the same PLC copolymer chains. The variety of chains accelerated some scientists like Brostow in [5,6] or Hess [7] to propose appropriate classification. Central to liquid crystalline properties is the anisotropy of shapes and interactions of molecules or their parts as in [8] and [9] by one of us. There are several theories of PLCs that help us to connect the macroscopic behavior to molecular structures and interactions. Important here is the statistical mechanical theory originally formulated by Flory in 1956 [10] and then developed further by him, his students, and his collaborators in Flory e.a. [11], Matheson e.a. [12,13], Brostow e.a. in [14,15]. Since PET has been used as a biomaterial [16,17,18] and PHB is an inert material [19], PLC here is tested as promising biomaterial [20,21].

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

Materials: The experimental material - copolymer of poly(ethylene) terephthalate PET + 0.6 mole fraction of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid PHB further in the text denoted as PET/0.6 PHB belongs to longitudinal thermotropic PLCs, the simplest type, with rodlike mesogens in the backbone and oriented along the backbone after one of us e.a. [22,23,24]. The PLC pellets were put through a high-speed thrashing machine and turned into a fibrous mass to avoid pre-aligning. This fibrous form of the PLC was kept in the temperature of 100°C for five hours to remove any excess water in a desiccator, before shaping. Glass fibres was provided by Cracow Academy of Mining with fibre diameter range 7 - 9 μm, average 8 μm, fibre length - 3 mm; data obtained with optical microscope Lanometr. It was tested four kinds of composite materials with 10, 15 and 25% of glass fibres and 10% of glass powder + PET/0.6 PHB. Besides was tested another type of PLC – PLA: poly(L-lactic acid) produced by DOW-Cargill (USA) and reinforced by 15% of glass fibre. Using in tests dumbbell samples were injected at temperature 180⁰–200⁰C. SEM micrographs of example tested material are shown in Fig.1, 2 [29].

Fig.1 SEM micrograph of PET/0.6PHB+10% glass powder, polished cross-section, 1000x

Fig.2 SEM micrograph of PET/0.6PHB+10% glass fibres, polished cross-section, 1000x

Tensile, relaxation and conductivity tests: Dumbbell samples (4 mm x 6.8 mm in crosssection and 50 mm length) were injected (injection temperature 180⁰-200⁰C). Tensile was carried out with ratio Vr = 2 mm/min using Zwick universal testing (Fig.3). Universal testing machine Instron was used for relaxation tests. Experiments were carried out at constant levels of strain $\epsilon = 0.5\%$ and 1%. Average time of measurement was 12 hrs. Calculation was done using Li's method [25]-Fig.4. Conductivity test was carried out in distil water (Fig.5).

Fig.4 Relaxation curves for the experimental materials in normalized half logarithmic system for two strain levels where: $\sigma_i^* = \sigma_i - \sigma_\infty$, $\sigma_0^* = \sigma_0 - \sigma_\infty$, and σ_∞ calculated using Li's method

Also in relaxation tests the PLC + 10% bioglass fiber blend revealed the best properties although the character of the relaxation curves was similar for all three materials. It has to be noted some test samples of pure PLC at the strain level $\epsilon = 1\%$ were destroyed at the beginning of relaxation tests.

Fig.5 Conductivity of pure PLC as a function of time.

The experiment was carried out during the period of 10 weeks. After the preliminary drop in conductivity caused probably by surface instability, the value equilibrated.

Injection molding and screws testing: The orthopedic screws (thread MW II) were injected from experimental material at the temperature of 185 °C (Fig.6). Shear tests was carried out with ratio $V_r = 2$ mm/min using Instron universal testing machine. After screws were planted into the bone, test was repeated with human bone as a counter-sample what simulated implantation case (Fig.7). Moment of torsion was obtained as a moment when the screw was destroyed. This test was done with using a special stand constructed on Krakow University of Technology [27,28].

Fig.6 The injected orthopedic screws.

Fig.7 a) the ultimate torque moment for bone - screw junction and b) shear with the direction along thread.

Some of the complications associated with the use of transpedicular screws for spinal fusions include the large diameters of the screws and screw breakage *in vivo*. Previous studies have identified the importance of the screw's geometric dimensions in contributing to the screw and surgical construct performance. Use of the recent advances of techniques take research on changes metal by appropriate plastic or carbon's composite. Fig.8 is shown direction for modelling of screw with a conical core and Fig.9 distribution of stresses for the same screw made of PET/0.6PHB+10% glass fibers [26].

Fig.8 Direction for modelling of screw with a conical core: a) view of screw, b) view of loading and fixing of connection screw-bone [26].

Fig.9 Distribution of stresses in a screw with a conical core made of PET/0.6PHB+10% glass fibers [26].

Fig.10 is shown thigh's bone of rabbit combined by PHB + 15% glass fiber (plate and screw) and Fig.11 preparation of thigh's bone of rabbit where it can be observed good adoption of using composite after 6 weeks since operation [27].

Fig.10 Thigh's bone of rabbit combined by PHB + 15% glass fiber, 4 weeks since operation.

Fig.11 Preparation of thigh's bone of rabbit, composite adopted, 6 weeks since operation, HE dye, 83x

CONCLUSION

Results obtained during the tests point at necessary reinforce matrix LPC polymers (PLA and PET/0,6PHB) by bioglass fibers that to get a better straight and modulus. Tests of the ultimate torment momentum for bone - screw junction and shear with the direction along thread show that PLA is material which can be more using in application on orthopedic screws (better values of M_s and F_s). It tries to make a material for orthopedic screws, which will have proprieties much similar to the bone. Relaxation tests did not revealed any dangerous behavior in the long term test. The promising preliminary results for conductivity tests open the door for biocompatibility tests which were tested and gave a positive results. Histopathological examination on rabbits proved the proper fixation of implants in bone tissue.

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